

Multi-Modal Multi-Party Interaction in the Flight Deck

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ABSTRACT

The rapidly growing air traffic density and the introduction of new technology have dramatically increased flight safety in the last 30 years while significantly increasing the complexity of the flying tasks and the flight deck human-machine interface. The modern business and air transport flight decks are equipped with displays acting as digital flight instruments, electronic maps, and documents instead of analog gauges, instruments, paper maps, and charts. These displays have GUIs based on point-and-click similar to desktop computers. One of the point-and-click paradigm limitations is that cursor pointing and data entry are relatively slow compared to other interaction means available these days and require a lot of head-down operation time while the head-up, out-of-the-window operation is critical for the pilot. Pilots also interact with other parties, such as Air traffic controllers (ATC). The information from ATC must be entered manually into the avionics by the pilot, which requires additional interaction steps and increases the pilot's workload.

In this paper, we introduce the Honeywell concept of multi-modal interaction for future flight decks that extend the interaction means with touch interaction and speech. Using speech-to-text technology makes it possible to perform efficient multi-modal and multi-party interactions between the ATC controller and pilot. Our multi-modal interaction technology enables advanced multi-modal interaction features such as combining modalities (cross-modal interaction) and utilization of anaphoric references by pronouns and keywords (anaphoric interaction) extended by using automatically transcribed information from the ATC controller using speech-to-text technology. All the above-mentioned advanced interaction means can be synergistically combined to provide a system with multi-modal multi-party interaction means.

We introduce a prototype of a Multi-modal Navigation Display capable of multi-modal moving map manipulation, graphical flight planning, and radio tuning. Then we describe a demonstration use-case on tuning the radio frequency using multi-modal multi-party interaction. Our multi-modal multi-party interaction approach addresses the increase of efficiency, decreasing human error and, as a result, lowering the pilot workload and maintaining safety.

KEYWORDS

Multi-modal, Multi-Party, Cross-modal, Anaphoric Interaction, Flight Planning, Speech recognition,

1 INTRODUCTION

Flight deck human-machine interfaces are designed with a paramount focus on safety and efficiency. The primary flight crew tasks are often referred as Aviate, Navigate, Communicate and Manage systems, with priority going from highest to lowest. From the human-machine interaction perspective, the flying operation is a complex multi-tasking and multi-device operation task; it

includes controlling and monitoring a large number of instruments or systems, cooperation of flight crew and air traffic control and monitoring and reacting to the situation outside the aircraft.

This paper describes the concept and prototype, showing how combining multi-party interaction with advanced multi-modal interaction can improve flight deck interaction efficiency and information flow. Improving efficiency is a primary way to decrease pilot workload, reduce human error, and maintain safety while increasing the flight deck's availability and integrity (robustness) of human-machine interface control by increasing input means redundancy.

1.1 State-of-the-Art Flight-deck Overview

The modern flight decks in business and air transport aircraft are equipped with digital flight instrument displays rather than analog dials and gauges. These flight decks are termed glass cockpits.

Glass cockpit typically consists of a Primary Flight Display (PFD) providing flight information, and Multifunction Display (MFD, also termed Navigation Display, ND) providing the pilots with navigation route, moving map, flight planning, or weather radar, to name a few navigation display functions. Navigation displays interaction is based on the WIMP graphical user interfaces and point-and-click paradigm. A keyboard and a cursor control device (CCD) are used as primary interaction means. The current interaction means brings a couple of limitations; navigation displays are equipped with many functions which, together with graphical user interfaces and cursor control devices, impact efficiency. Many functions are accessible through time-consuming visual navigation (e.g., hierarchical menus) and pointing using a cursor control device which is a relatively accurate but slow input device. All the pointing in GUI requires the pilot to gaze on display (head-down interaction) instead of providing the pilot the maximum time to look out the windows (head-up) which is essential for the pilot, especially during taxi, take-off, approach, and landing phases of flight.

Most of the current business and air transport aircraft are designed for the crew consisting of two pilots – pilot flying and pilot monitoring. Each pilot has its Primary flight display (PFD), with the main flight information like speed, altitude, crew alerting system, and horizontal situation indicator. Furthermore, there are usually two multifunction display units (MFD in the middle with navigation information, flight plan, electronic checklist, and input parameters.

Figure 1 - Position of Primary Functional Display (PFD) and Multi-Function Display (MFD) in the cockpit of Falcon F900

1.2 Graphical Flight Planning

Flight planning task refers to the flight's planning, navigation, and management, which represents one of the most important tasks in the flight deck (see the aviate/navigate/communicate/manage systems above). The flight plan describes the flight route. A route is planned ahead of take off, however, the flight plan is managed during the flight as well (e.g., changes in route due to constraints or to save fuel, establishing a holding before approach and landing if the airport landing runway is busy). Most commercial flights represent flying between airports. The route is shown on the lateral moving map, and to help with planning, there are geographical waypoints (WPT). These waypoints define the flight route. There are situations when it is necessary to change flight plan because of weather or surrounding traffic.

Before the rise of glass cockpits, flight planning was done manually on paper. With glass cockpits, the flight planning can be done on Multifunction display.

The flight plan is shown on the map (See Figure 2), and the user can move the map or rotate it, zoom in and out for an appropriate view of the flight route. Graphical Flight Planning (GFP) includes a selected set of functions, including Direct To, Cross, Hold, Amend Route and Offset.

Figure 2 - Graphical Flight Plan Example

1.3 Air Traffic Control

Air Traffic Control (ATC) is a service executed by ground-based air traffic controllers who direct aircraft on the ground and through controlled airspace. The primary purpose of ATC is to prevent collisions, manage air traffic flow, and provide pilots with information and other support. (Eurocontrol, 2018).

An air traffic controller (ATCco) is always assigned to a part of the airspace. ATCco is responsible for navigating the aircraft on the ground or in the air, ensuring spacing among all aircraft, and preventing collisions. ATCco must quickly deal with unexpected circumstances such as emergencies, weather changes, and unscheduled traffic and keep the flow expeditious. They monitor the position of the aircraft (visually, if on the ground, or

Lufthansa 54A runway 24 left cleared for take-off wind 130 degrees 6 knots.

Figure 3 - Example of a communication from ATCco to pilot.

the display, if in the air), its speed, direction, and other parameters. In general, the ATCco serves as a navigator; the pilot is always the final authority in charge and may deviate from ATCco instructions.

The communication between ATCco and pilots goes via radio channel and they use English as the official language, but in some cases native language is also possible. See Figure 3 for an example of ATCco communication.

Several ATCco categories may differ from region to region (e.g., at busy airports, there is a more detailed structure). Each category has its frequency number, and the pilot can tune in as needed:

- Area controller – Controls aircrafts at high altitudes.
- Approach controller – Manages airspace close to the airport.
- Tower controller – Takes over the communication when the aircraft is between 10 and 15 miles from landing or is going to take off.
- Ground controller – Controls the aircraft when it is on the ground.

Figure 4 - ATCo categories (ATC Careers, 2018).

Various English accents, communication speed, and noise in the cockpit are several factors that can influence the correct understanding of communication. The pilot usually has a piece of paper and writes down all the instructions from ATCo. Each instruction pilot must read back to ATCo to ensure it has been correctly understood. Our multi-party multi-modal approach is designed to simplify the entire process and increase efficiency.

2 Multi-modal Flight Deck

2.1 Multi-modal Flight Deck Philosophy

The state-of-the-art glass cockpit human-machine interfaces are primarily based on the point-and-click paradigm, which is not always the optimal way to conduct flight deck tasks. The graphical user interface on multifunction displays (MFD) is typically controlled by the cursor-control device (CCD) with buttons and a keyboard. Similarly to a mouse on a desktop computer, information and functions can be accessed through a cursor designation in the display units. Thus, the Cursor Control Device (CCD) is the primary input device controlling glass cockpit displays. There are two CCDs and two associated cursors in the cockpit. When its trackball is rolled, a corresponding cursor moves in the display.

The cursor is used in the displays for:

- Pointing
- Activating an item
- Selecting or de-selecting an item using the <ENTER> button on the CCD,
- Modify a value on a data field, thanks to the data SET rotator on the CCD.

Figure 5 - Cursor Control Device (CCD) in Dassault F900 aircraft

However, these traditional input devices, together with the growing amount of presented information, are not the most efficient method to control all the features provided by the display. For example, pointing by a cursor control device or navigation within extensive hierarchical menus is time-consuming and motorically difficult and inherently increases the head-down time and pilot workload [3]. Therefore, novel approaches and concepts are being considered to make the interaction more efficient and reduce workload and pilot error. Advances in novel interaction means such as speech, and touch interaction is not yet common in avionic displays (as opposed to consumer electronics).

Modality combinations can offer more efficient ways to conduct certain types of tasks (e.g., spatial tasks using touch, and verbal tasks using speech). Modality combinations also provide an opportunity to balance better each modality's benefits and limitations (e.g., CCD is slow and accurate versus touch, which is fast but less accurate). Another key benefit of the multi-modal approach is the possibility of addressing operational conditions. For example, if turbulences occur, the pilot may prefer to switch from touch to CCD as CCD offers higher accuracy during vibrations in the flight deck compared to touch. Multimodality also offers a personalized user experience – the pilot has multiple options for conducting the task. The pilot may choose a modality according to personal preferences and habits (e.g., a pilot may prefer speech over touch).

New technology penetrates the aviation industry significantly slower than in the consumer area due to specific technical, regulatory, and certification requirements of the safe-critical industry. A few of the most modern business jet aircraft are equipped with touch-resistive technology displays, and there are a few displays that support simple speech commands.

The Honeywell multi-modal interaction approach goes further than introducing new modalities that exist as parallel modalities only. The concept aims at fine-grained (see below), highly integrated, and synergistic interaction capabilities. To further describe the philosophy, we introduce the following fundamental design principles:

Legacy Interaction Means Respect

The current flight-deck environment contains many legacy designs since the flight deck philosophy has evolved incrementally rather than disruptively (as it is more common in the consumer sector). The rules and principles were established through many years of development in all areas of the flight environment, not just the flight deck itself. The pilot interaction in the flight deck is not defined by the pilot interacting with the flight deck instruments only but also with the other components of the flight environment (e.g., ATC – Air Traffic Control) and according to the procedures, rules, and regulations. For these reasons (i.e., legacy and environment), the multi-modal flight deck should primarily be compatible with the existing flight environment. Thus, our fundamental approach is to build on the existing flight deck HMI and extend or modify it with new interaction concepts rather than reinventing the flight deck from scratch.

The Honeywell multi-modal flight deck concept retains most of the legacy of the state-of-the-art glass cockpit interaction concept. Thus, it is largely backward compatible with the traditional flight deck HMI while providing significant extensions by introducing new modalities and establishing advanced multi-modal concepts such as cross-modal interaction or anaphoric interaction, as discussed below.

Primary and Secondary Modalities

Traditional modalities, keyboard, and CCD, are considered primary – these modalities are intended to control all critical functions. New modalities, touch and speech, are considered secondary – primary modalities always back them up.

Consistency

New modalities and advanced multi-modal interaction enable new interaction methods and patterns that should be consistently implemented across all possible flight deck functions.

Striving for Efficiency and Naturalness

The introduction of new modalities is pragmatic – we are adding new modalities and combinations of modalities to (1) better balance the benefits and weaknesses of individual modalities, (2) enable interaction patterns that provide more efficient interaction (e.g., faster task times, fewer errors) which in result contributes to lowering workload, (3) provides the pilot with the possibility to select the modality according to personal preferences and (4) provides the pilot with the possibility to switch between modalities according to operational conditions.

A new level of efficiency is also provided by enabling advanced multi-modal interaction means – See cross-modal interaction and Anaphoric interaction. To further support the efficiency and naturalness, the voice interaction (or cross-modal interaction containing voice) should be concise while providing an adequate level of flexibility in utterances syntax and enabling unambiguous interpretation of user input by the underlying technology.

Smart and Context-aware Interaction

The underlying technology tracks context information (e.g., from other subsystems) to improve the efficiency of interaction. For example, the user does not need to specify parts of utterances that could be automatically inferred or disambiguated by the underlying technology using contextual information and other support or

configuration knowledge. Among other capabilities, context awareness is demonstrated in Anaphoric interaction; see below.

Advanced Fine-grained Multimodality

Multi-modal systems can be characterized by interaction granularity as coarse-grained or fine-grained. Coarse-grained systems provide parallel modalities with no or limited capability to combine modalities in utterances. Fine-grained systems provide multi-modal utterances, consisting of partial inputs from multiple modalities or contextual information. In Honeywell's multi-modal interaction approach, the advanced multimodality is provided by cross-modal and Anaphoric interaction.

2.2 Advanced Multi-modal Features

Cross-modal Interaction

Cross-modal interaction represents an interactive feature that makes it possible to use multi-modal utterances. Individual components of an utterance can be entered using different modalities. A cross-modal interaction is typically beneficial if a given utterance is entered more efficiently when modalities are combined. For example, executing the DIRECT TO function on the BEBKU waypoint (waypoint names are constituted as five letter sequences) is significantly more efficient when done cross-modally than if provided entirely by speech. Using speech pilot should specify the waypoint using spelling out the ICAO alphabet (ICAO) letters (this is how the waypoints are communicated with ATC as well). Thus the utterance will be "DIRECT TO BRAVO ECHO BRAVO KILO UNIFORM." Using cross-modal interaction, the pilot can highlight the waypoint by tapping on the display or using a CCD device and then say "DIRECT TO" only. The underlying technology will associate these partial inputs from individual modalities and understand the input as "DIRECT TO BEBKU."

Anaphoric Interaction

Anaphoric interaction builds on cross-modal interaction capability. Anaphora are pronouns such as THIS, IT, HERE, THERE, ON THIS, ON THAT [5, 6] or keyword objects (e.g., TOWER FREQUENCY) that can be associated with relevant information or object representing the keyword object value. For example, if the user says "TUNE THIS ON VHF" then the system will try to associate "THIS" with a selected or highlighted object using CCD or touch if possible.

2.3 Multi-modal Interaction Manager

Multi-modal Interaction Manager (MIM) is the Honeywell proprietary enabling technology for multi-modal flight deck interaction. The MIM manages input modalities, prioritization, and disambiguation and performs a fusion of modalities. The fusion allows cross-modal interaction and anaphoric interaction. MIM also provides Natural Language Processing (NLP) capabilities, context data processing (e.g., routing speech-to-text data to be associated using multi-party multi-modal fusion), and output management. The MIM is utilized in Honeywell multi-modal prototypes such as the Multi-modal Navigation Display described in the following section.

2.4 Multi-modal Navigation Display

The concept and prototyping of multi-party multi-modal interaction are demonstrated on a prototype of multifunction display (MFD), see Figure 6. However, the concept described in this paper and the design principles are reusable for the other flight deck parts.

The multi-modal navigation display uses Multi-modal Interaction Manager (MIM) to implement multi-modal interaction capabilities and provides the following applications:

Lateral Moving Map application – allows the pilot to manipulate the moving map and display various map layers (e.g., setting the visibility of the terrain layer).

Graphical Flight Planning application – includes a selected set of flight planning functions, which allows the pilot to interact with the flight plan.

Software Radio Control application – allows the pilot to control the VHF panel, tune frequencies and check transcribed communication between ATC and pilot. These applications can cooperate and share parameters. For example, copying the frequency from transcribed communication to the VHF text box is possible. The pilot has several options on how to interact with the applications.

Figure 6 – Prototype of Multi-modal Navigation Display

3 MULTI-PARTY MULTI-MODAL INTERACTION

The following section describes the concept of multi-party multi-modal interaction and introduces a use-case on radio tuning using a Multi-modal Navigation Display. Pilot communication includes communication with the other pilot in the flight deck and with the ATC controllers who direct aircraft. The ATC controller informs the pilot about the relevant radio frequencies for the given area. Currently, the frequency information is received from the ATC controller using radio. The pilot listens to the radio and then manually enters the frequency on the radio (either on the radio or using Multifunction Navigation Display, if supported). The pilot should either remember or write down the frequency to be able to enter it and then to the radio.

Using Multi-modal Navigation Display, the multi-party multi-modal interaction makes the radio tuning significantly easier; The

radio frequencies are recognized using the speech-to-text technology receiving the ATC controller communication over the radio. These frequencies are automatically provided to the Multi-modal Interaction Manager, which processes the user input. Then the pilot can use speech to directly tune the relevant frequency without remembering it and even without specifying the frequency using numbers. The high-level architecture is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7 – Multi-party multi-modal System Components

An efficient combination of advanced multi-modal interaction capabilities such as cross-modal interaction or anaphoric interaction and contextual information (e.g., data provided by speech-to-text technology transcribing the ATC controller communication) makes possible multi-party multi-modal interaction in the flight deck.

Pronouns and keywords can be used as anaphora. Pronouns (as THIS, IT, HERE, THERE, ON THIS, ON THAT) can be used for the specification of the source object and/or specification of the target object.

As a source object for anaphora, any HMI control that contains a valid radio frequency and that has been selected in a relevant time window (approximately when the user was saying the pronoun, to put it in simple terms) can be used.

As a target object, any HMI control that is used to enter a radio frequency and that has been selected in a relevant time window can be used (in the current grammar, there is currently only one such object supported – the VHF frequency text box)

There could also be the source and target anaphora in a single utterance (e.g., TUNE THIS ON THAT) where THIS represents source anaphora and THAT means target anaphora, see example below.

Besides the pronoun-based anaphoras, the keyword-based anaphoras are supported. For the radio tuning use case, the radio frequency designating names can be used (e.g., TOWER, OR TOWER FREQUENCY). The complete grammar for setting the radio frequency is depicted in Figure 8. Relevant objects for anaphoras should be highlighted using CCD or touch on the screen or referenced by their name.

Figure 8 – Anaphoric interaction for tuning the radio frequency

Figure 9 – Multi-party multi-modal radio tuning example with single anaphora

Figure 10 - Multi-party multi-modal radio tuning example with double anaphora

Figure 9 depicts an example of an utterance with single anaphora. When the pilot leaves the area, the ATC controller informs the pilot about the next radio frequency – 118.1 MHz. This information is automatically recognized using speech-to-text technology. When

the pilot says "COPY GROUND ON VHF, "the GROUND serves as designating object anaphora for ground frequency which the MIM associates with a 118.1 MHz value. Without multi-party multi-modal interaction, the pilot must manually enter the frequency using the keyboard and CCD.

A more advanced example is provided in Figure 10. The pilot says "TUNE THIS ON THAT" which represents an utterance with double anaphora – THIS and THAT. The system will associate "THIS" and "THAT" with inputs from other modalities at relevant time windows. Since the user was first pointing to the frequency number and then to the VHF text box, the system will understand the user input as: "COPY 118.1 ON VHF" (TUNE and COPY commands are synonyms).

4 DISCUSSION

In aviation, the primary design objective is to maintain safety. In the human-machine interface design, the primary way to maintain safety is by maintaining or reducing the pilot (crew) workload. It can be achieved by increasing the efficiency of interaction (e.g., task times), reducing human error, and providing natural interaction means that best suit the type of task (e.g., spatial tasks, verbal tasks, fill-in tasks, or check tasks).

Multi-modal interaction is extending interaction means to fit better the tasks in the flight deck and better balance individual modalities' benefits and limitations. Fine-grained multi-modal interfaces open the efficiency improvement opportunity to a higher level. Combining modalities in a single utterance can be significantly more efficient than entering it using one modality. Specifying a flight planning function using speech while selecting a waypoint using touch instead of spelling the waypoint using individual ICAO letters using speech can be an illustrative example of combining modalities.

Anaphoric interaction, as an extension of the fine-grained cross-modal interaction, provides a vital opportunity for workload reduction by avoiding the necessity to specify object values directly (e.g., a radio frequency). Abstract pronouns with multi-modal fusion capabilities will automatically do the association between the pronoun and object value.

Multi-party interaction, as a synergistic extension of multi-modal anaphoric interaction, provides a whole new level of use-cases and design opportunities to improve the flight deck human-machine interaction efficiency. While in the current flight decks, the radio tuning task is a sequence of listen-understand-remember-enter-apply-check (while utilizing multiple cognitive channels and resources), with multi-party anaphoric interaction, the task is reduced to receive-enter-apply-check steps, which provides a significant simplification. Importantly, the multi-modal multi-party interaction opens a whole new design space for the principal change of task interaction in the flight deck.

In past years, we did several human factors and usability-related studies, controlled experiments, and flight tests on multi-modal concepts and prototypes. Since this paper primarily describes our concept and approach to multi-modal and multi-party interaction, the detailed description of studies and experiments exceeds the space and scope of this paper. Briefly, the experiments have shown that there are up to 1.7x faster task times on touch, speech and multi-modal moving map manipulation compared to CCD and

keyboard, 1.5x times faster flight planning operations and up to 2x times faster multi-party multi-modal radio tuning while lowering the workload and increasing the head-down time for some of the functions.

5 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper introduced the concept and approach for fine-grained multi-modal interaction for future flight decks. While we have demonstrated the concept on a prototype of the Multi-modal Navigation Display, the approach is replicable to other elements of flight deck human-machine interfaces such as instruments or instrument panels. Besides identifying and exploring new use cases and applications, this area represents the primary focus for future work.

Honeywell multi-modal technology supports advanced multi-modal features such as cross-modal interaction and anaphoric interaction that can be used to implement multi-party interaction. Multi-modal multi-party interaction has the potential to provide higher efficiency and lower workload pilot operations.

There is, however, another significant objective on the longer-term scale with even more opportunity for multi-modal and multi-party interaction in the flight deck – the reduced crew operations. Although most of the current business- and air transport-aircraft flight decks are designed for a two-pilot crew, there is a growing interest in reduced crew aircraft (i.e., pilot and flight assistant crew) or a single pilot aircraft. For the reduced crew operation aircraft, there is a huge challenge related to maintaining safety and workload. To achieve this goal, significantly more powerful automation, and highly efficient human-machine interfaces will be the key enablers of the reduced crew operation aircraft in the future. The high level of context awareness of the presented multi-modal, multi-party technology will allow more efficient human-machine collaboration between the pilot and other parties, including automation as another crucial element of the future flight deck. Multi-modal multi-party interaction can be one of the pillars for the future reduced crew operation flight decks providing a high level of efficiency and low workload operation.

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